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Review Article

MANAGEMENT OF PERITONSILLAR ABSCESS

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Abstract:

Introduction: The palatine tonsils represent an important part of the lymphoid tissue in Waldeyer's ring. They are positioned in a strategic location in the oropharynx, they are often exposed to both inhaled and ingested antigens and accomplish localized immune functions. This exposure to potential pathogens and involvement in local processing of microorganisms could be the foundation for the high numbers of tonsillar infections. Acute tonsillitis is considered a highly prevalent and expensive condition that affect kids, adolescent and adults. In the US, more than eighteen million patients sought care for acute tonsillitis in 1996, making it the 6th main reason for physician consultations [3]. It is estimated that 4 to 6 times more individuals do not seek medical care for a sore throat. The condition could be even more prevalent in other countries such as Denmark, as about 425,000 rapid streptococcal antigen detection tests (RADT) are done by Danish general practitioners yearly, to diagnose infection with Group A Streptococci (GAS) [VII]. Peritonsillar abscess (PTA), also known as quinsy, refers to a collection of pus located between the tonsillar capsule and the pharyngeal constrictor muscle. It is commonly considered as a complication of acute tonsillitis though some investigators have found evidence pointing to a role of the salivary glands in the soft palate (Weber's glands) in the pathogenesis of this condition. Though the prognosis is believed to have been good, serious complications are also reported in the literature over the last three centuries. Recently, lethal outcome of PTA is extremely rare. But, in spite of improvements in living conditions and general health (including oral hygiene), the ease of access to medical care, and the invention and widespread use of antibiotics, PTA is still relatively frequent (approximately 2000 cases annually in Denmark). Aim of work: In this review, we will discuss the management of peritonsillar abscess. Methodology: We did a systematic search for the management of peritonsillar abscess using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles. Conclusions: The palatine tonsils represent an important part of the lymphoid tissue in Waldeyer's ring. They are positioned in a strategic location in the oropharynx, they are often exposed to both inhaled and ingested antigens and accomplish localized immune functions. This exposure to potential pathogens and involvement in local processing of microorganisms could be the foundation for the high numbers of tonsillar infections. Acute tonsillitis is considered a highly prevalent and expensive condition that affect kids, adolescent and adults. We discussed the most recent evidence regarding the management of peritonsillar abscess. The regular history of patients with PTA is 3 to 6 days of progressive sore throat, pain on swallowing to the point of being unable to eat, ear pain, malaise, and trismus. Severe acute tonsillitis involving infectious mononucleosis (IM) have several similar symptoms and findings of PTA involving sore throat, pain on swallowing, ear pain, malaise, discomfort, dehydration, tonsillar exudates, tender and enlarged cervical lymph nodes, and fever. Recently, there are 3 established approaches of draining PTAs: needle aspiration, ID, and acute tonsillectomy. Additionally, to surgical drainage, antimicrobial therapy is proposed. The preferred antibiotic regimen varies between countries and centers. Penicillin, either oral or intravenous.

Key words: *peritonsillar abscess, pathophysiology presentation, management, surgery.*

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INTRODUCTION:

The palatine tonsils represent an important part of the lymphoid tissue in Waldeyer's ring [1]. They are positioned in a strategic location in the oropharynx, they are often exposed to both inhaled and ingested antigens and accomplish localized immune functions [2]. This exposure to potential pathogens and involvement in local processing of microorganisms could be the foundation for the high numbers of tonsillar infections. Acute tonsillitis is considered a highly prevalent and expensive condition that affect kids, adolescent and adults. In the US, more than eighteen million patients sought care for acute tonsillitis in 1996, making it the 6th main reason for physician consultations [3]. It is estimated that 4 to 6 times more individuals do not seek medical care for a sore throat [4]. The condition could be even more prevalent in other countries such as Denmark, as about 425,000 rapid streptococcal antigen detection tests (RADT) are done by Danish general practitioners yearly, to diagnose infection with Group A Streptococci (GAS) [VII].

Peritonsillar abscess (PTA), also known as quinsy, refers to a collection of pus located between the tonsillar capsule and the pharyngeal constrictor muscle. It is commonly considered as a complication of acute tonsillitis though some investigators have found evidence pointing to a role of the salivary glands in the soft palate (Weber's glands) in the pathogenesis of this condition [5]. Though the prognosis is believed to have been good, serious complications are also reported in the literature over the last three centuries. Recently, lethal outcome of PTA is extremely rare. But, in spite of improvements in living conditions and general health (including oral hygiene), the ease of access to medical care, and the invention and widespread use of antibiotics, PTA is still relatively frequent (approximately 2000 cases annually in Denmark) [I].

In this review, we will discuss the most recent evidence regarding the management of peritonsillar abscess.

METHODOLOGY:

We did a systematic search for the management of peritonsillar abscess using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

The terms used in the search were: peritonsillar abscess, pathophysiology presentation, management, surgery.

Signs and symptoms of peritonsillar abscess

The regular history of patients with PTA is 3 to 6 days of progressive sore throat, pain on swallowing to the point of being unable to eat, ear pain, malaise, and trismus⁶. About forty percent of patients have received antibiotic therapy within one week before the presentation. Patients are commonly found clearly ill, uncomfortable, dehydrated, and in pain [7]. Examination of the oropharynx often shows tonsillar exudates and asymmetric, indurated peritonsillar swelling with deviation of the tonsil and uvula to the midline.

Other not uncommon symptoms are tender and enlarged cervical lymph nodes, trismus, muffled voice, and fever. Noteworthy upper airway obstruction is seldom observed.

Differential diagnoses of peritonsillar abscess

Severe acute tonsillitis involving infectious mononucleosis (IM) have several similar symptoms and findings of PTA involving sore throat, pain on swallowing, ear pain, malaise, discomfort, dehydration, tonsillar exudates, tender and enlarged cervical lymph nodes, and fever. The diagnosis could be even more challenging to differentiate from acute peritonsillitis, in which the infection has already spread to the peritonsillar tissue, however without abscess formation. In acute peritonsillitis there are additional signs such as trismus and asymmetric peritonsillar swelling with deviation of the tonsil and uvula, but the peritonsillar induration might be

absent. It looks apparent that acute tonsillitis, acute peritonsillitis, and PTA are entities within a continuous spectrum, and an infection may progress through these three stages if left untreated or even despite antibiotic management.

Complications of peritonsillar abscess

Complications of PTA are comparatively rare. They can involve parapharyngeal abscess (PPA) [8], upper airway obstruction[9], Lemierre's syndrome (LS), necrotizing fasciitis [10], mediastinitis ¹¹, erosion of the internal carotid artery, brain abscess, and streptococcal toxic shock syndrome [12].

Diagnostic tools in peritonsillar abscess

The differentiation between acute peritonsillitis and PTA depend on the result of a needle aspiration (+/- pus), though false negative results could be due to insufficient technique or atypical abscess location. Otherwise, contrast-enhanced computer tomography (CT) or ultrasound could be used to see a PTA. Because these radiological examinations are not helpful in the drainage of a PTA, at our institution they are only done if PPA or other complications are suspected.

Instead, following a day without progress despite intravenous antibiotic management, patients are checked and managed under general anaesthesia. PPA situated near the tonsillar bed could be challenging to differentiate from PTA until surgical exploration.

Microbiology of peritonsillar abscess

GAS is the only bacterium, which is recognized as pathogen in PTA. But, studies of PTA aspirates reveal that most abscesses present without evidence of GAS involvement. A potential role for anaerobes has been proposed by several investigators, but there was a lack of convincing evidence for individual pathogens [13]. So, about eighty percent of PTA patients have an invasive infection with undefined bacterial pathogens.

Identifying significant pathogens, other than GAS, is crucial to deploy this great potential for improvement in timely antibiotic management with avoidance of infectious spread and abscess development. Moreover, complications secondary to PTA could be avoided or better controlled if more pathogens in PTA are recognized.

Surgical treatment of peritonsillar abscess

Hippocrates performed what is believed to be incision of PTAs in the fourth century BC. The first complete acute tonsillectomy (à chaud) for the

management of a PTA was done by Chausaignac in 1859. It was not until a number of publications in the period 1910 to 1935 verified the safety and effectiveness of the technique that it was adopted by a number of surgeons in Europe and the United States as the main technique for PTA management. It is challenging to approximate the percentage of PTA patients who were managed with acute tonsillectomy or incision and drainage (ID).

Recently, there are 3 established approaches of draining PTAs: needle aspiration, ID, and acute tonsillectomy. None of these techniques has been known as the surgical treatment. Acute tonsillectomy can be performed carefully and requires only a brief hospitalization ¹⁴. The process ensures complete drainage of the abscess regardless of position relative to the tonsil and removal of the infectious load within the tonsils. Hence, there is no need for postoperative antibiotic therapy in uncomplicated cases [15].

Antimicrobial treatment of peritonsillar abscess

Additionally, to surgical drainage, antimicrobial therapy is proposed. The preferred antibiotic regimen varies between countries and centers. Penicillin, either oral or intravenous, was the first choice for sixty five percent of responders. In Denmark, combined treatment with penicillin and metronidazole was preferred by fifty eight percent of responders. However, multiple antibiotic regimens are reported in recently including but not limited to intravenous penicillin alone, amoxicillin with clavulanic acid with or without metronidazole, cefuroxime and metronidazole ¹⁶, and clindamycin.

Challenges in studying the microbiology of peritonsillar Abscess

There are many difficulties, which need to be addressed, when studying PTA microbiology. Some difficulties are due to the fact that several factors influence the microbiological findings and others are linked to the complexity of the infection.

Diagnostic precision

All patients should suffer from the same diagnostic entity. But, differential diagnostic problems are common in PTA patients because of the similarity to acute tonsillitis and acute peritonsillitis, which are possibly entities within a continuous spectrum. Clinical examination and radiological modalities are flawed in the differentiation between acute peritonsillitis and a minor (or even medium-sized) PTA. So, recognizing of pus is important for diagnostic reliance in studies of PTA. In fifteen percent of cases, the PTA is located at the lower tonsillar pole and it is very difficult or even

impossible to perform an aspiration in local anaesthesia [17].

Number of patients

The number of patients is not a difficulty specific to studies of PTA microbiology, however it should, of course, be reflected and depending on the type of study and the issue(s) in focus, the number of patients needed can be difficult to achieve.

Normal tonsillar flora

The tonsils are usually heavily and diversely colonized. Often, bacteria thought to have pathogenic possible and importance can also be found in non-infected and healthy tonsils [18]. Henceforth, tonsillar infections could be resulting from the normal flora.

The polymicrobial nature of PTA

A polymicrobial mixture of aerobes and anaerobes could be collected from the majority of PTA aspirates, if cultures involve both aerobic and anaerobic incubation. Concurrent Epstein- Barr virus (EBV) infection is also a rare finding.

Change in significant pathogens during PTA development

During the period of infection and abscess growth (typically four to seven days), a change in important microbes could occur.

Influence of current or recent antibiotic treatment

Inclusion of patients with antibiotic management before collection of specimens could also change the microbiologic results and cover up the right microbe.

CONCLUSIONS:

The palatine tonsils represent an important part of the lymphoid tissue in Waldeyer's ring. They are positioned in a strategic location in the oropharynx, they are often exposed to both inhaled and ingested antigens and accomplish localized immune functions. This exposure to potential pathogens and involvement in local processing of microorganisms could be the foundation for the high numbers of tonsillar infections. Acute tonsillitis is considered a highly prevalent and expensive condition that affect kids, adolescent and adults. We discussed the most recent evidence regarding the management of peritonsillar abscess. The regular history of patients with PTA is 3 to 6 days of progressive sore throat, pain on swallowing to the point of being unable to eat, ear pain, malaise, and trismus. Severe acute tonsillitis involving infectious mononucleosis (IM) have several similar symptoms and findings of PTA involving sore throat, pain on swallowing, ear pain,

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